

Access to Online Social Media Sources Improve English Learners' Vocabulary Skills

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Abstract: *The purpose of this research study was to highlight the importance of online social media sources in English language vocabulary development at university level. The study was descriptive in nature that is why self-developed questionnaire was used for the collection of data as a research instrument. Population of the study was all the master level students enrolled in session 2015-16 of social sciences and pure sciences in public sector universities, and sample size of the present study was eight hundred students of four public sector universities of southern districts in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Similarly, the data which was collected from the given sample of population was arranged, coded, analyzed, and tabulated through SPSS version 24. Statistical tools which were used for analysis of the present data were percentage, mean, standard deviation, independent sample t-test, and one way ANOVA post hoc. Result of the study showed positive effect.*

Key Words: University level learners, Access to Social media, English language Vocabulary

Introduction

Learning from various online social media sites is very important because it develops the creative power of the learners and increases their level of understanding while reading new words of vocabulary, watching new images, and listening of sounds and pronunciation styles of various native and non-native speakers of English language (khan et al, 2016). Media use is not only useful for English language learners but also for those teachers who teach English to because the English teachers may get help from socials media sources like new methods of teaching English, new words of vocabulary, new styles, and similarly, various online workshops and seminars which are helpful for them regarding English language teaching to university level learners. Teachers get help from online sources and then they use these new trends in education on their students (Aydin, 2012). Thorne (2010) suggested the reason of social media familiarity is that social media is used to develop relationship through online communication and online. It is used to maintain relationship and is used for social interaction. The various social media sources are used for variety of purposes like classroom activities, social interaction, social awareness, and familiarity. Similarly, it is used for sharing of information and other necessary posts and pictures (Facer & Abdous, 2011). Social media sources like Facebook facilitate the learners and help them in learning process. As Yu, Tian, Vogel and Kwok (2010) also described the role of social networking that social media sources and especially the online social networking are the sources of autonomous learning and self-initiated learning. It is that source which makes them able improve their vocabulary and share their views and maintain personal links with others. Similarly, a large amount of vocabulary grammatical knowledge is there available on internet the learners may download various topics and grammatical rules and then they may share it with other friends and class-fellows for their extension of knowledge and information about that topic or field of interest through the help of social media source like Facebook (Valentine & Repath-Martos, 1997). As it is mentioned above the features and advantages of social media tool Facebook in English as foreign language learning i.e. writing assignments, sharing of information, development of vocabulary, and so many other benefits the other important one is that it builds positive attitudes of students. Shih (2011) described in his experimental study that the use of Facebook in English language learning plays an important role and said that it develops the positive attitudes of the English

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learners besides another advantages of social media sources in English language learning. Similarly, Another study which was conducted by [Al-Shehri \(2011\)](#) on male university level students highlighted that social media sources like Facebook plays an important role in English language learning. The findings of the study highlighted that learning through Facebook is new for English language learners and it is interested for English language learners. Learning through Facebook facilitate the English language learners and provide the English language learners opportunities to improve their vocabulary and get relevant information about the surrounding which are helpful for them in English language learning process ([Brady et al. 2010](#)).

Review of Literature

Online social media sources plays an important role in English language learning process because it facilitate learners to improve their learning of foreign or second language. According to new modern approach outside the classroom conversation is more beneficial for English learners as compare to classroom discussion. Social media based language learning enables the EFL learners to get benefits from those material which are already available on internet, and improve their language learning skills i.e. listening, speaking, reading, writing, and language learning competencies i.e. grammar competency and vocabulary building which using the various online sources (Krashen, 1988). You Tube is one the most important sites of social networking and play an important role in English language learning because the English learners may easily download videos from the You Tube and then they may learn English language from this video which are shared by teachers or other language exports for the help and support of the English language learners ([Irfan et al. 2016](#)). The other important point regarding the You Tube application is that it is useful for English language teachers because the English language teachers use important video of English language in the classroom like video which are related to the pronunciation practice or different techniques which are used for language fluency and learners may get help from these video in order to improve their pronunciation, Grammar, vocabulary, listening, speaking, reading and writing skills of English language in a very easy and systematic manner ([Brady et al. 2010](#)).

Throne, (2009) has reported that blogs are used for many purposes in respect of language learning. Teachers and learners both use Facebook for variety of purposes like language learning assessment, practice of English language vocabulary, repetition of words, and making sentences. Different topics may be discussed in blogs which is written in blogs and the EFL learners may present their comments on various topics and paragraphs which improve the reading and writing skills of EFL learners. Hui-Ju Wu and Pai-Lu Wu (2011) also find the trend that blogging plays a pivotal role in language learning. He has highlighted in his research study that blogs play a dominant role in reading and writing skills development of English learners, but the importance of blogging may not be ignored in vocabulary development of English learners. Blogs help the English learners to develop vocabulary, increase reading speed, develop proper use of grammar and enhance the reading comprehension of the EFL learners (Steven, 2009).

Sykes et al. (2008) A also in their study revealed that computer-mediated communication tools are helpful in the study of language learning, and the practice of text-based chatting and multiple online gaming and mobile devices are also very helpful for them. Those learners who use social media sources like Facebook are more talented in reading and writing skills of English language because they do practice of reading and writing properly and use new words and vocabulary in writing skills ([Bakar et al. 2010](#)).

It is not only difficult to utilize media sources in classroom activities but a challenge also like print media or electronic media but so far as the application of social media is concerned than we may not wrong to say that social media sources are useful and easy for English language learners like Facebook use or twitter etc. (Shirley Biagy, 1996) described that media plays an important role in Education and facilitate the learners in teaching learning process and help them to improve their vocabulary. Media is use for entertainment of learners and increases the potential of learners. There are a number of online sites through which the English learners may get help easily ([Aydin. 2012](#)).

Objectives of the Study

1. To find out the role of access to online social media sources for English language vocabulary development at university level (across gender group).
2. To find out the role of access to online social media sources for English language vocabulary development at university level (across discipline).
3. To make appropriate recommendations based on the findings of the study

Hypothesis of the Study

4. There is no significant difference in access to online social media sources for English language vocabulary development at university level. (Across gender group).
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2. There is no significant difference in access to online social media sources for English language vocabulary development at university level. (Across discipline).

Methodology

Population of the study was all the student of public sector universities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa enrolled in MA, M.Sc. programs session 2015-16. The study was descriptive in nature that is why self-developed questionnaire was used for the collection of data and finally data was collected from only 789 respondents both social sciences and pure sciences across gender groups. The researcher used one and same questionnaire for collection of data from the students of both social sciences and pure sciences. The validity and reliability of the modified questionnaire was checked in pilot study. The reliability of the questionnaire items were estimated with Cronbach's Alpha. The data was collected through questionnaire in this way that the researcher explained orally the statements of questionnaire to the respondents and then the learners filled the questionnaires according to the given instruction and then the collected data was analyzed through statistical techniques like mean, standard deviation, independent T-test. In order to perform these statistical tools the researcher used SPSS (version-24).

Results

Graph 1:

Table 1. Use of Social Media Sources for English Language Vocabulary Development

Scale used	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Never	15	1.9	1.9	1.9
Rarely	21	2.7	2.7	4.6
Sometimes	162	20.5	20.5	25.1
Often	389	49.3	49.3	74.4
Always	202	25.6	25.6	100.0
Total	789	100.0	100.0	

In the above table 1 views of respondents regarding vocabulary development through use of social media sources are presented. Those learners who never use social media sources for English language vocabulary development are zero, those who rarely use various social media sources for English language vocabulary development are 10 1.3%, those learners who use sometimes were 179, 22.7%, those learners who often use social media sources for English language vocabulary development were 282, 35.7%, and those learners who always use various social media sources for English language vocabulary development were only 318 out of 789 which is 40.3% of the total sample of population. Thus in light of the above detail it may not be wrong to say that most of learners use various social media sources for English language vocabulary development but still there are a large number of learners who are never use or rarely and or only sometime use social media sources for English language speaking skills development.

Table 2. Usefulness of Social media Sources of English Language Vocabulary Development

Scale Used	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Not at all helpful	39	4.9	4.9	4.9
Slightly Helpful	33	4.2	4.2	9.1
Somewhat helpful	109	13.8	13.8	22.9
very Helpful	439	55.6	55.6	78.6
Extremely Helpful	169	21.4	21.4	100.0
Total	789	100.0	100.0	

The above table 2 clearly indicated the views of learners regarding the improvement of English language vocabulary through online social media channels. The detail of learners are in light of five point likert scale are given below: Total number of responses regarding social media sources not at all helpful for English language vocabulary development were 39, 4.9%, slightly helpful were 33, 4.2%, somewhat helpful responses were 109, 13.8%, very helpful responses were 439, 55.6% and extremely helpful responses were 169, 21.4%. Thus in light of the above views of the respondents it may not be wrong to say that social media sources are very helpful for English language vocabulary development.

Table 3. Usefulness of Social Media Sources for English Language Learning Across gender groups (t-test)

English Language Skills & Competencies	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F	Sig.
Vocabulary Development	Female Students	389	4.0720	.84032	41.542	.000
	Male Students	400	3.6200	1.00654		
	Female Students	389	3.9100	.87321		

The above table 3 in vocabulary development male students mean 3.6200, female students mean 3.9100 std. deviation of male students 1.00654, and std. deviation of female students .87321, F-value 41.542, P-value is .000.

Table 4. Usefulness of Social Media Sources for English Language Learning Across discipline

English Language Skills & Competencies	Discipline	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F	Sig.
Vocabulary Development	Pure sciences	389	3.8586	.92673	.326	.568
	Social Sciences	390	3.7744	1.02682		
	Pure sciences	389	3.7455	.88778		

The above table 4 in vocabulary development social sciences students mean 3.7744, pure sciences students mean 3.7455 std. deviation of social sciences students 1.02682, std. deviation of pure sciences students .88778, F-value .326, and P-value is .568.

Table 5. Usefulness of Social Media Sources for English Language Learning Across gender groups (ANOVA)

English Language Skills & Competencies	Gender Wise Groups	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Vocabulary Development	Between Groups	16.588	1	16.588	18.648	.000
	Within Groups	700.091	787	.890		
	Total	716.679	788			

The above table 5 of ANOVA application showed the views of gender groups regarding the usefulness of various social media sources in English language skills and competencies development which the researcher has selected for this present study. In vocabulary development sum of squares between groups 16.588 and within groups 700.091, total 716.679 mean square 16.588 and .890, F-value 18.648, P-value .000. Thus in the above table of ANOVA application there is significance in views of learners that is why the hypothesis were accepted that there is no significant difference between the views of male and female learners regarding usefulness of social media sources for English language skills and competencies development because in all statement p-value is .000 which is less than critical threshold 0.05.

Table 6. Usefulness of Social Media Sources for English Language Learning Across gender groups (ANOVA)

English Language Skills & Competencies	Discipline Wise groups	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Vocabulary Development	Within Groups	741.367	786	.943	.401	.670
	Total	741.825	788			
	Between Groups	.731	2	.366		
	Within Groups	715.948	786	.911		
	Total	716.679	788			

The above table 6 of ANOVA application reflected the views of discipline groups regarding the usefulness of various social media sources in English language skills and competencies development which the researcher had selected for this present study. In vocabulary development sum of squares between groups .731 and within groups 715.948, total 716.679 mean square .366 and .911, F-value .401, P-value .670. Thus in the above table of ANOVA application there is insignificance in views of learners that is why the hypothesis is rejected that there is no significant difference between the views of social sciences and pure sciences learners regarding usefulness of social media sources for English language skills and competencies development because p-value in all statements is greater than critical threshold 0.05.

Table 7. Effect of Social media Sources on English Language Vocabulary Development across Gender groups

Questionnaire statements	Gender groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	F	Sig.
My vocabulary language has increased due to the use of various social media sources.	English Male Students	400	4.1725	.58189	787	18.433	.000
	Female Students	389	4.2828	.63994	775.346		

Use of social media sources helped me to learn new vocabulary of English language.	Male Students	400	4.1700	.59749	787	14.644	.000
	Female Students	389	4.2828	.63994	779.757		
I use social media sources to read my friends' opinions about several issues in order to increase my vocabulary of English language.	Male Students	400	4.1725	.58189	787	23.038	.000
	Female Students	389	4.3008	.64578	773.607		
Social media is an important source for English language vocabulary development.	Male Students	400	4.1725	.58189	787	16.503	.000
	Female Students	389	4.2751	.63726	776.110		
I read different text materials by using social media sources to increase my English language vocabulary.	Male Students	400	4.1725	.58189	787	14.620	.000
	Female Students	389	4.2674	.63448	776.881		
Social media sources may be used to increase my English language vocabulary.	Male Students	400	4.1725	.58189	787	17.536	.000
	Female Students	389	4.2699	.64348	774.303		
Social media have become an important source of English language vocabulary development.	Male Students	400	4.1725	.58189	787	18.201	.000
	Female Students	389	4.2725	.64440	774.028		
Social media is my first choice to find new learning strategies for my vocabulary building.	Male Students	400	4.1825	.58742	787	15.049	.000
	Female Students	389	4.2828	.63994	777.035		
I use social media to get new information which improve my vocabulary of English language.	Male Students	400	4.4125	.69177	787	15.424	.000
	Female Students	389	4.4344	.59113	774.247		
Social media is an important platform that allows us to improve our English language vocabulary.	Male Students	400	4.1725	.58189	787	24.997	.000
	Female Students	389	4.2931	.65525	770.594		

The above table 7 of t-test application clearly indicates the views of university level learners across gender groups regarding the role of social media sources in English language vocabulary development. The results of the study in light here showed that there was no significant difference between the views of male and female learners because in all the above ten statements the F-value is greater than p-value like in first statement the F-value is 18.433, and P-value is .000, in second statement F-value is 14.644, and P-value is .000, in third statement F-value is 23.038, and P-value is .000, in fourth statement F-value is 16.503, and P-value is .000, in fifth statement F-value is 14.620, and P-value is .000, in sixth statement F-value is 17.536, and P-value is .000, in seventh statement F-value is 18.201, and P-value is .000, in eighth statement F-value is 15.049, and P-value is .000, in ninth statement F-value is 15.424, and P-value is .000, in last statement F-value is 24.997, and P-value is .000. Thus it is also accepted because p-value in all statements is .000 which is less than critical threshold 0.05. It showed that there is no significant

difference in views of learners regarding effect of various social media sources in English language vocabulary development across gender groups at university level.

Table 8. Effect of Social media Sources on English Language Vocabulary Development across Discipline groups

Questionnaire statements	Discipline	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	F	Sig.
My vocabulary English language has increased due to the use of various social media sources.	Social Sciences	390	4.1564	.69788	777	29.019	.000
	Pure sciences	389	4.3290	.47047	682.242		
Use of social media sources helped me to learn new vocabulary of English language.	Social Sciences	390	4.1538	.71122	777	33.046	.000
	Pure sciences	389	4.3290	.47047	674.946		
I use social media sources to read my friends 'opinions about several issues in order to increase my vocabulary of English language.	Social Sciences	390	4.1564	.69788	777	24.260	.000
	Pure sciences	389	4.3470	.47664	687.230		
Social media is an important source for English language vocabulary development.	Social Sciences	390	4.1487	.69403	777	24.865	.000
	Pure sciences	389	4.3290	.47047	684.364		
I read different text materials by using social media sources to increase my English language vocabulary.	Social Sciences	390	4.1564	.69788	777	33.845	.000
	Pure sciences	389	4.3136	.46456	677.375		
Social media sources may be used to increase my English language vocabulary.	Social Sciences	390	4.1462	.69643	777	24.339	.000
	Pure sciences	389	4.3265	.47499	686.698		
Social media have become an important source of English language vocabulary development.	Social Sciences	390	4.1462	.70011	777	27.367	.000
	Pure sciences	389	4.3290	.47047	681.018		
Social media is my first choice to find new learning strategies for my vocabulary building.	Social Sciences	390	4.1667	.70285	777	34.996	.000
	Pure sciences	389	4.3290	.47047	679.513		
I use social media to get new information which improve my vocabulary of English language.	Social Sciences	390	4.3205	.71512	777	70.104	.000
	Pure sciences	389	4.5630	.49666	693.579		
Social media is an important platform that allows us to improve our English language vocabulary.	Social Sciences	390	4.1564	.69788	777	21.045	.000
	Pure sciences	389	4.3393	.49013	697.779		

The above table 8 of t-test application clearly indicates the views of university level learners across discipline regarding the role of social media sources in English language vocabulary development. The results of the study in light here highlighted that there is no significant difference between the views of social sciences and pure sciences learners because in all the above ten statements the F-value is greater than p-value like in first statement the F-value is 929.019, and P-value is .000, in second statement F-value is 33.046, and P-value is .000, in third statement F-value is 24.260, and P-value is .000, in fourth statement F-value is 24.865, and P-value is .000, in fifth statement F-value is 33.845, and P-value is .000, in sixth statement F-value is 24.339, and P-value is .000, in seventh statement F-value is 27.367, and P-value is .000, in eighth statement F-value is 34.996, and P-value is .000, in ninth statement F-value is 70.104, and P-value is .000, in last statement F-value is 21.045, and P-value is .000, thus it is accepted because p-value in all statements is .000 which is less than critical threshold 0.05 which shows the significance of results. It showed that there is no significant difference in social sciences and pure sciences learners regarding effect of various social media sources in English language vocabulary development at university level.

Table 9. Effect of Social media Sources on English Language Vocabulary Development across gender groups

Questionnaire Statements	Gender wise groups	ANOVA			F	Sig.
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square		
My vocabulary English language has increased due to the use of various social media sources.	Between Groups	2.398	1	2.398	6.420	.011
	Within Groups	293.992	787	.374		
	Total	296.390	788			
I use social media sources to read my friends' opinions about several issues in order to increase my vocabulary of English language.	Between Groups	2.508	1	2.508	6.551	.011
	Within Groups	301.335	787	.383		
	Total	303.843	788			
Social media is an important source for English language vocabulary development.	Between Groups	3.245	1	3.245	8.601	.003
	Within Groups	296.907	787	.377		
	Total	300.152	788			
Social media sources may be used to increase my English language vocabulary.	Between Groups	2.075	1	2.075	5.579	.018
	Within Groups	292.666	787	.372		
	Total	294.740	788			
Social media have become an important source of English language vocabulary development.	Between Groups	1.774	1	1.774	4.794	.029
	Within Groups	291.293	787	.370		
	Total	293.067	788			
I use social media to get new information which improve my vocabulary of English language.	Between Groups	1.872	1	1.872	4.981	.026
	Within Groups	295.756	787	.376		
	Total	297.627	788			
Social media is an important platform that allows us to improve our English language vocabulary..	Between Groups	1.972	1	1.972	5.239	.022
	Within Groups	296.213	787	.376		
	Total	298.185	788			
Use of social media sources helped me to learn new	Between Groups	1.983	1	1.983	5.262	.022
	Within Groups	296.572	787	.377		

vocabulary of English language.	Total	298.555	788			
I use social media sources to read my friends 'opinions about several issues in order to increase my vocabulary of English language.	Between Groups	.095	1	.095		
	Within Groups	326.516	787	.415	.229	.632
	Total	326.611	788			
Social media is an important source for English language vocabulary development.	Between Groups	2.866	1	2.866		
	Within Groups	301.689	787	.383	7.477	.006
	Total	304.555	788			

The above table 9 of one way ANOVA application shows the views of gender groups regarding the role of social media in English language vocabulary development at university level in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The views of learners are collected in five point Likert scale Strongly Disagree to strongly agree. The results of the study here revealed that there was insignificance in results of the above table like in first statement the F-value is 6.420, and P-value is .011, in second statement F-value is 6.551, and P-value is .011, in third statement F-value is 8.601, and P-value is .003, in fourth statement F-value is 5.579, and P-value is .018, in fifth statement F-value is 4.794, and P-value is .029, in sixth statement F-value is 4.981, and P-value is .026, in seventh statement F-value is 5.239, and P-value is .022, in eighth statement F-value is 5.262, and P-value is .022, in ninth statement F-value is .229, and P-value is .632, in last statement F-value is 7.477, and P-value is .006. Thus it is partially accepted because in some statements p-value is less than critical threshold but in rest of nine statements p-value is greater than critical threshold 0.05. It showed that there is significant difference in views of learners between groups and within groups across gender groups regarding effect of various social media sources in English language vocabulary development at university level.

Table 10. Effect of Social media Sources on English Language Vocabulary Development across Discipline groups

Questionnaire Statements	Discipline Wise groups	ANOVA			F	Sig.
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square		
Social media is an important source for English language vocabulary development.	Between Groups	21.050	2	10.525		
	Within Groups	275.341	786	.350	30.045	.000
	Total	296.390	788			
Social media is an important source for English language vocabulary development.	Between Groups	21.192	2	10.596		
	Within Groups	282.651	786	.360	29.465	.000
	Total	303.843	788			
Social media is an important source for English language vocabulary development.	Between Groups	22.544	2	11.272		
	Within Groups	277.608	786	.353	31.915	.000
	Total	300.152	788			
Social media is an important source for English language vocabulary development.	Between Groups	21.484	2	10.742		.000
	Within Groups	273.256	786	.348	30.899	
	Total	294.740	788			
Social media is an important source for English language vocabulary development.	Between Groups	19.870	2	9.935		
	Within Groups	273.197	786	.348	28.584	.000
	Total	293.067	788			
Social media is an important source for English language vocabulary development.	Between Groups	21.421	2	10.710		
	Within Groups	276.207	786	.351	30.479	.000
	Total	297.627	788			
	Between Groups	21.634	2	10.817		

Social media is an important source for English language vocabulary development.	Within Groups	276.551	786	.352	30.744	.000
	Total	298.185	788			
Social media is an important source for English language vocabulary development.	Between Groups	20.507	2	10.253		
	Within Groups	278.048	786	.354	28.985	.000
Social media is an important source for English language vocabulary development.	Total	298.555	788			
	Between Groups	31.968	2	15.984		
Social media is an important source for English language vocabulary development.	Within Groups	294.643	786	.375	42.640	.000
	Total	326.611	788			
Social media is an important source for English language vocabulary development.	Between Groups	21.888	2	10.944		
	Within Groups	282.667	786	.360	30.431	.000
Total	304.555	788				

The above table 4.70 of one way ANOVA application shows the views of discipline groups regarding the role of social media in English language vocabulary development at university level in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The views of learners are collected in five point Likert scale Strongly Disagree to strongly agree. The results of the study highlighted that there was no significant difference between the views of social sciences and pure sciences learners because in all the above ten statements the F-value is greater than p-value like in first statement the F-value is 30.045, and P-value is .000, in second statement F-value is 29.465, and P-value is .011, in third statement F-value is 31.915, and P-value is .000, in fourth statement F-value is 30.899, and P-value is .000, in fifth statement F-value is 28.584, and P-value is .000, in sixth statement F-value is 30.479, and P-value is .000, in seventh statement F-value is 30.744, and P-value is .000, in eighth statement F-value is 28.985, and P-value is .000, in ninth statement F-value is 42,640, and P-value is .000, in last statement F-value is 30.431, and P-value is .000. Thus it is accepted because in all ten statements p-value is .000 which is less than critical threshold 0.05. It showed that there is no significant difference in social sciences and pure sciences learners between groups and within groups regarding effect of various social media sources in English language vocabulary development at university level.

Finding / Results

- The findings of this study highlighted the importance of online social media sources for English language vocabulary development at university level in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.
- The findings of the study highlighted that there is not a significant difference between the views of male and female learners regarding the usefulness of social media sources for English language vocabulary development at university level.
- The findings of the study highlighted that there is not a significant difference between the views of social sciences and pure sciences students regarding the use of social media for English language vocabulary development at university level.
- The findings of the study indicated that the use of social media sources for English language vocabulary development is not only positive in social sciences but also in pure sciences, and similarly, not only for male learners but also for female learners according the views of learners regarding access to online social media for English language vocabulary skills development at university level.

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